

THERAVĀDA AND MAHĀYĀNA PERSPECTIVES ON LUMBINI: A COMPARATIVE HISTORICAL AND ARCHAEOLOGICAL STUDY

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Abstract

The birthplace of the Buddha, which called Lumbini, is one of the most sacred Buddhist pilgrimage sites in the world, present day in Nepal. This dissertation article examines the Theravāda and Mahāyāna perspectives on Lumbini by historical, textual, and archaeological analysis. Theravāda traditions mainly describe in the Pali Texts like, Lumbini as a historical and sacred place connected with the life of the Buddha, while Mahāyāna traditions explain in the Sanskrit literature, that it through Bodhisattva ideals and devotional stories. This research uses qualitative and comparative methods based on Pāli Canonical texts, Mahāyāna literature, archaeological reports, and modern scholarly studies. The main Important archaeological findings, for examples- the Aśokan pillar inscription and the marker stone of the Birth of the Prince Siddhatha, excavation discoveries, support the historical authenticity of Lumbini as the birthplace of the Buddha. The study concludes that, although Theravāda and Mahāyāna traditions have different doctrinal interpretations, both traditions deeply respect Lumbini as a shared Buddhist heritage site and an important symbol of unity, pilgrimage, and spiritual value for Buddhists around the world.

Keywords: *Lumbini, Theravāda Buddhism, Mahāyāna Buddhism, Buddhist Pilgrimage, Archaeology, Aśokan Pillar, Buddhist Heritage, Birthplace of the Buddha.*

Introduction

Lumbini, universally recognized as the birthplace of the Buddha, which located in present-day Nepal, holds a central place in Buddhist pilgrimage, both Theravāda and Mahāyāna traditions revere Lumbini, though they interpret its historical, doctrinal, and symbolic

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significance in different ways (Strong 12). Most of the Theravāda sources emphasize Lumbini as a historically verifiable site associated with the birth place of the Buddha, while Mahāyāna literature presents as more expanded narrative linked to the Bodhisattva ideal¹ and devotional symbolism (Bechert 76).

This study aims to examine these perspectives through a comparative analysis grounded in historical records and archaeological evidence. Both traditions recognize Lumbini as a sacred place, they interpret its historical, doctrinal, and symbolic significance in different ways, and according to Theravāda Pali Canon emphasize Lumbini as a historical pilgrimage site and Mahāyāna Sanskrit texts expand its important through Bodhisattva ideas, and miraculous events (Trainor 98). This study seeks to examine these perspectives through a comparative analysis grounded in historical records, textual traditions, and archaeological evidence.

Statement of the Problem

Although Lumbini has been extensively studied from historical and archaeological viewpoints, there is limited research that integrates these findings with a comparative doctrinal analysis of Theravāda and Mahāyāna traditions (Coningham and Young 54). This article seeks to bridge this gap by examining how textual traditions and material evidence together shape the understanding of Lumbini as a sacred Buddhist site on the ground. This is the limited research article paper because, it systematically compares Theravāda and Mahāyāna interpretations of Lumbini while integrating archaeological findings with textual evidence. This research article mentioned the gap, by exploring how historical data and material culture connecting with doctrinal perspectives in shaping the understanding of Lumbini in different Buddhist traditions (Strong 63).

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the historical development of Lumbini as a Buddhist sacred site.
2. To do the analytical study of Theravāda textual interpretations of Lumbini based on Pāli sources.
3. To study Mahāyāna perspectives on Lumbini through selected Sanskrit Buddhist texts.
4. To evaluate archaeological evidence in relation to both traditions.

Research Questions

1. How is Lumbini described in early Theravāda Buddhist texts?

¹ **Bodhisattva ideal:** In Mahāyāna Buddhism, the Bodhisattva ideal refers to the aspiration and practice of attaining Buddhahood for the benefit of all sentient beings through compassion, wisdom, and the perfection of virtues (pāramitās).

2. How do Mahāyāna Sanskrit sources interpret and explain about the significance of Lumbini?
3. How archaeological evidences support for the historical authenticity of the birth place of the Buddha?
4. How influence the doctrinal perspectives to the interpretation of archaeological data?
5. In what ways does Lumbini function as a shared yet diversely understood sacred space?

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative and comparative research method. Primary sources include Pāli Canonical texts and selected Mahāyāna Buddhist literature in translation (Rhys Davids 210). Archaeological reports, inscriptions, and site studies related to Lumbini are used as material evidence (Coningham and Young 87). Secondary scholarly works support for the important historical and doctrinal analysis to confirming the birth place of the Buddha, and this research analysis will involve textual comparison, historical contextualization, and interpretation of archaeological data.

Significance of the Study

This research contributes to Buddhist Studies by offering a balanced understanding of Lumbini as a shared sacred space interpreted through different doctrinal lenses (Trainor 120). It also highlights and mentioned about the important role of archaeology in supporting and contextualizing religious narratives (Coningham and Young 96). The research is relevant for students of Buddhism, archaeology, heritage studies, and inter-sectarian understanding.

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to Theravāda and Mahāyāna perspectives on the Birth place of the Buddha, Lumbini, focusing by historical, textual, and archaeological aspects. Contemporary political or tourism-related issues are beyond its scope.

Expected Outcome

This study is expected to demonstrate that whatever the Theravāda and Mahāyāna traditions differ in interpretive focuses, archaeological evidence provides a common historical foundation, and Lumbini emerges as a unifying yet diversely understood sacred site within Buddhism (Strong 91).

Conclusion

The birth place of the Buddha, Lumbini, is one of the most sacred places in Buddhist history. This study analysed the Theravāda and Mahāyāna point of view on Lumbinī through historical, textual, and archaeological concepts. According to Theravāda traditions mainly

present Lumbinī as a historical pilgrimage site connected with the life of the Buddha, while Mahāyāna traditions explain it with broader Bodhisattva ideals and miraculous narratives (Strong 45).

This study also states that archaeological evidence, especially the inscription of Aśokan pillar and excavation findings, such as marker stone of the Birth place of the Buddha,² which supports the historical authenticity of Lumbinī as the birthplace of the Buddha (Coningham and Young 112). Even the two Buddhist traditions differ in doctrinal interpretation, both deeply respect Lumbinī as a sacred Buddhist site. In conclusion, Lumbinī can be understood as a shared Buddhist heritage site where historical evidence and religious traditions come together, moreover, it remains a symbol of unity, pilgrimage, and spiritual importance for Buddhists around the world.

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² The Aśokan pillar at Lumbinī, erected by Emperor Aśoka in the third century BCE, contains an inscription identifying the site as the birthplace of the Buddha. Modern archaeological excavations, including the discovery of a marker stone and ancient structural remains beneath the Māyā Devī Temple, further support the historical authenticity of Lumbinī as the Buddha's birthplace.